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Clinico-etiological classification of epilepsy in children presenting to specialty epilepsy clinic at tertiary medical center

Umesh Joshi, Nitish Vora and Aasheeta S Shah

Smt. NHL Municipal Medical College, India

Introduction: Epilepsy is one of the most urgent problems in pediatric neurology. Asserting the causes and types of seizure is important for diagnostic purposes and for evaluating therapy. Objectives: To identify the clinical & etiological profile of children and the characteristics of seizures in them along with therapeutic responses.

Methods: All patients who attended the epilepsy clinic & fulfilled the selection criteria were enrolled in study. This is a descriptive study of 12 months (June'15–June'16) & involved analysis of records of the patients who came to specialty OPD. Three groups were formed accordingly—focal, generalized & unknown onset with further etiological sub-divisions—Genetic, Structural/Metabolic, Immune, Infectious & Unknown.

Results: In all, 417 patients were studied. The distribution as per clinical presentation was- group I (generalized) 215 (58.5%)—group II (focal) 154 (36.9%), and group III (unknown) 48 (4.6%). The main etiologies were perinatal asphyxia (28.3%), NHBI (11.4%) in (structural–metabolic) sub group. In Genetic & Infectious, Channelopathies (10.5%) & Post Meningitis Sequelae (4.7%). 56.3% of the patient in group II were on more than 3 AEDs. 14.3% in group I were weaned of AEDs. 61.4% patients in group II were having neuro-developmental sequelae. EEG revealed abnormal activity in 30 (6.2%) in group I & 31 (19.3%) in group II. Maximum patient with refractory epilepsy were seen in group III.

Conclusion: To have a good management of epilepsy, we need to have multi-dimensional classification of epilepsy based on both clinical & etiological spectrum. Perinatal asphyxia & NHBI are one of the most common yet avertible etiologies.

Biography

Umesh Joshi is Post-graduate specialty resident in Pediatrics Department at the V S General Hospital, Ahmedabad. He received his MBBS from Smt. NHL Municipal Medical College and is currently pursuing MD from V S General Hospital. He completed his schooling from prestigious Sacred Heart Convent School and Delhi Public School, New Delhi. He had attended numerous seminars on autistic spectrum disorders and presented same in national conferences. He was given AAP certified Neonatal Resuscitation Program Certificate in 2015. He had been currently working under renowned Epileptologist Dr. Nitish Vora for 1 year. Apart from medicine, he had special interests in music and tennis.

ujoshi.md@gmail.com

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